

Eastern England SDE Scaling Safe Outputs with SACRO integration

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VISTA SACRO Workstream Final Report

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1. Executive summary

This report presents the Eastern England Secure Data Environment's (EE-SDE)¹ implementation and evaluation of SACRO², the semi-automated statistical disclosure control (SDC) toolset developed through the DARE UK TRevolution programme. As part of the VISTA project, SACRO was operationalised within live EE-SDE analytical and governance workflows to understand how semi-automated output checking can enhance the safety, efficiency and consistency of research output egress, while maintaining robust human oversight and public trust.

The workstream adopted a practitioner-centred approach, engaging both researchers and airlock managers to test how ACRO, SACRO Viewer, and accompanying documentation could be integrated into established analysis pipelines and review processes. Researchers were trained by EE-SDE as part of platform onboarding and airlock managers received SDC training delivered by the University of the West of England (UWE). Ongoing support is enabled through enhanced EE-SDE documentation, and community resources such as the SDC Handbook³ and Statbarn⁴. These provide a strong foundation for users to understand both the principles and operational steps of SDC. Structured testing using synthetic Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) based data^{5,6}, alongside real project workflows, enabled the team to evaluate SACRO across a range of statistical outputs, from descriptive tables and regression models to survival analyses and visualisations.

Findings show that SACRO enhances transparency and auditability by packaging outputs with clear risk summaries, metadata and logs, reducing manual burden for routine statistical outputs and enabling more consistent reviewer triage. Researchers found ACRO easy to adopt within existing R and Python workflows, while airlock managers reported clearer evidence paths and improved consistency for supported outputs. Testing also highlighted that SACRO does not yet accommodate the full diversity of analytical outputs used in health research, particularly bespoke visualisations and more complex modelling approaches. This finding reinforces the value of maintaining robust manual review pathways in the short term.

The report concludes with recommendations for continuous improvement within the EE-SDE, and for wider adoption across the TRE community, emphasising shared principles, consistent training, transparent governance and scalable, sustainable SDC processes.

2. Project background

VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025 Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TRevolution standards and AI capabilities within the EE-SDE.

The aims of VISTA were to support and enhance existing EE-SDE processes. Demonstrating how large-scale AI-enabled research can be conducted safely, efficiently and consistently, whilst helping other TREs adopt these approaches. There were four specific aims:

- To complete a structured self-assessment against the SATRE benchmark specification and develop actionable recommendations to inform the next phase of TRE development
- Test and refine semi-automated research output checking in the EE-SDE
- Safely train and export ML and AI models from the TRE
- Support readiness for AI models to be deployed in NHS services

VISTA adopted three TRevolution capabilities: SATRE⁷ aligns the EE-SDE with a community driven specification adopted across UK TREs and now evolving to include federation and ML output control capabilities. SACRO enables more efficient and auditable disclosure checking by applying SDC principles directly within analytical workflows. SACRO-ML⁸ extends this to ML models through ante-hoc and post-hoc risk assessments, including SafeModel evaluation and membership inference attack testing.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) was embedded through existing EE-SDE structures, including the Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG). This ensured that development of SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML reflected public expectations around transparency, accountability and appropriate use of automation.

This report outlines the work of the EE-SDE to operationalise SACRO and presents feedback from researchers and airlock managers on the tool's functionality and training materials.

3. Methodology and approach

The SACRO workstream adopted a practitioner-centred approach that focused on understanding how researchers and airlock managers engage with semi-automated SDC tools in real analytical and governance workflows. The methodology combined structured onboarding and hands-on tooling evaluation to establish how ACRO, SACRO Viewer, supporting documentation and community resources could be integrated into the EE-SDE's operational processes in a scalable and sustainable way.

3.1. Airlock manager training and engagement

The workstream began by preparing airlock managers to assess outputs generated through ACRO and reviewed using SACRO Viewer. Initial onboarding included training delivered by the UWE team, introducing core SDC concepts and the practicalities of reviewing analytical outputs. This foundational training was complemented by the enhanced documentation available from autumn 2025, which provided clearer walk-throughs of ACRO behaviours, disclosure thresholds and the structure of SACRO artefacts. This updated documentation was produced in response to feedback from VISTA and the wider TRE community members.

Airlock managers also leveraged community-produced resources, including the SDC Handbook and <https://outputchecking.org/> website to help understand the disclosure risk of different statistical methods and graphs. These community resources support consistent interpretation of disclosure risks across airlock managers by providing clear definitions. These materials were supplemented with EE-SDE-specific Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and the newly expanded documentation formed a comprehensive support ecosystem that guided reviewers through both automated and manual SDC checks following EE-SDE's safe outputs process.

As part of the engagement process, structured feedback was obtained from airlock managers to assess the interpretability of ACRO outputs, the usability of SACRO Viewer, and the extent to which documentation and training prepared them for reviewing increasingly complex outputs. Airlock managers were asked to reflect on how ACRO-generated artefacts aligned with existing airlock procedures, whether structured risk summaries reduced manual effort, and which areas continued to rely on judgement or required additional context from researchers. This feedback informed the ongoing refinement of SOPs, reviewer guidance, and the development of supplementary training materials.

3.2. Researcher training and engagement

Researcher engagement began with the integration of ACRO training materials into the EE-SDE knowledge base, drawing on both existing SDC resources and newly updated documentation provided by the UWE team in autumn 2025 through sacro-tools.org. These materials significantly improved the clarity and accessibility of tool-specific guidance and ensured that researchers were supported by a consistent, authoritative set of instructions when applying SDC techniques within their workflow.

To test the practicality of these materials, the workstream recruited researchers from live and pipeline projects in the EE-SDE. This ensured that testing reflected real analytical practices, data types and project timelines. Researchers were encouraged to replace parts of their existing analytical methods with the ACRO equivalents, for example, substituting standard summary-table or regression functions with ACRO wrapper

functions. This approach enabled the team to observe not only whether researchers could technically adopt the tools, but how the tools integrate into their established analytical routines.

Throughout the testing period, researchers had access to worked examples, knowledge base documentation, and a synthetic dataset to trial workflows without risk. Qualitative feedback was collected through email exchanges and informal check-ins, capturing researcher perspectives on usability, clarity of documentation, ease of integrating ACRO into existing scripts and the extent to which the tooling aligned with their methodological needs. This feedback also informed recommendations on features requiring refinement and additional training resources needed to support broader adoption.

3.3. Structured testing with synthetic data

To complement the real-world researcher testing, the VISTA team conducted structured end-to-end testing of SACRO using realistic analytical workflows applied to synthetic data. This testing was designed to mirror real-world research activity while ensuring that the evaluation could proceed without governance delays or risks associated with disclosive content. Synthetic datasets based on the OMOP Common Data Model were used to replicate typical health research structures and enable testing across a wide range of statistical and modelling approaches.

In the R-based workflow, testing centred on an anaemia-focused analytical use case examining demographic and clinical risk factors such as Type 2 diabetes, hypertension and heart failure, alongside machine learning-based prediction of anaemia status. This use case enabled the team to evaluate SACRO across outputs that closely reflect the diversity of real-world research, including descriptive frequency tables, regression models, interaction terms, survival analyses, count models, visualisations and machine learning outputs. The objective extended beyond confirming tool compatibility to examining the practical challenges and considerations researchers encounter when incorporating ACRO into established analytical workflows. Details of these tests can be found in Appendix 1.

4. EE-SDE disclosure control documentation and training

Our approach to preparing researchers and airlock managers for SACRO adoption combined practical, action-oriented platform guidance with principles-based training and documentation provided through the wider SDC community. Task focused documentation in the EE-SDE knowledge base gave users clear instructions on how to complete essential steps, such as preparing outputs, staging files, or interpreting SACRO artefacts. Foundational resources, including the SDC Handbook, Statbarn and the SACRO technical guides, explain the reasoning behind SDC thresholds, risk categories and audit requirements and provide deeper information on how SACRO functions.

Training introduced the underlying concepts that shape disclosure control, while documentation supported users in applying these concepts consistently in day-to-day practice. This dual structure ensures that the operational materials remain concise and easy to follow, while still giving users access to more detailed explanations whenever they wish to strengthen their understanding. In combination, these resources make it possible for users to work safely and confidently and allow SACRO to be integrated into analytical and governance workflows at scale.

4.1. Airlock manager training

When new airlock managers are onboarded, they participate in training sessions delivered by the University of the West of England (UWE) team, who maintain several of the disclosure control tools used across TREs. These sessions introduce the core principles of SDC, including common disclosure risks, responsibilities under the Five Safes framework⁹, and practical approaches to reviewing analytical outputs. The training also introduces tools used within the EE-SDE output-checking workflow, including Statbarn, ACRO, and the SACRO Viewer application.

4.2. Airlock manager documentation

The EE-SDE provides a structured suite of documents¹⁰ that guide airlock managers through every stage of SDC. These materials combine operational steps with governance expectations so that reviewers can make consistent, transparent, and auditable decisions when assessing outputs for release. This documentation is built on top of the foundational references such as the SDC handbook, sacro-tools.org and outputchecking.org and is meant to act as process guidance for the airlock managers rather than replicating foundational knowledge.

The airlock manager SOP sets out the full review pathway from submission to final sign-off (Figure 1). It explains the evidence researchers should supply, how reviewers interpret that information, and how decisions are recorded and confirmed. In practice, the SOP walks reviewers through a sequence of actions designed to ensure safe and defensible release. These steps include:

- Checking that the researcher has provided all required submission materials
- Retrieving submitted outputs and applying SDC checks, including assessment of secondary disclosure risks
- Recording a justified decision that clearly explains the reviewer's reasoning and any required mitigations
- Requesting independent confirmation from a second airlock manager under the four-eyes principle for consistency and assurance
- Escalating borderline or novel cases to the Data Management Team, and if required, to the DAC Chair for a final governance determination

This documentation ensures that all reviewers follow a shared, repeatable workflow aligned with the EE-SDE governance framework.

The operational review guide supports airlock managers in navigating the platform and carrying out technical elements of the review. As reviewers move between analytical environments, platform tools, and governance systems, the guide outlines how to:

- Interpret a new platform egress request and review the associated service desk ticket
- Update ticket ownership and access the governance virtual desktop
- Mount the quarantine location and examine the staged files submitted by the researcher
- Run or interpret automated scans where relevant
- Apply practical SDC checks across different output types, including:
 - Tables: small cell protection, dominance checks, reconstruction using totals
 - Visualisations: outliers, sparse groups, rare categories
 - Narrative: unique combinations or inadvertently identifying text

By combining platform steps with SDC criteria, the guide ensures systematic consideration of primary, attribute, and secondary disclosure risks.

Figure 1: High-level overview of the airlock output review process within the EE-SDE, showing key stages from submission through to disclosure assessment, decision-making, and release.

The decision framework provides a consistent approach for categorising review outcomes and recording the rationale behind each decision, covering both ACRO and non-ACRO routes. The primary reviewer undertakes the initial assessment and then transfers the files to the independent secondary reviewer. It is the primary

reviewer who communicates with the researcher wherever additional information is needed, including ensuring that the README contains sufficient detail to enable appropriate disclosure control.

For non-ACRO submissions, reviewers manually assess each file and confirm that no elements pose a disclosure risk, such as small numbers or identifiable combinations.

For ACRO submissions, reviewers use the SACRO Viewer to interpret disclosure risk:

- Pass: may proceed to approval
- Review: requires documented judgement and may involve targeted mitigation
- Fail: cannot be released
- Mixed outputs: only Pass items may be approved

The airlock manager must still confirm that Pass items contain no annotations or additional context that SACRO could not detect and provide feedback explaining why Review and Fail items are not suitable for release. Reviewers must also check whether combining these outputs with previously released material could create secondary disclosure risks.

Once the primary and secondary reviewers reach consensus, the final decision is recorded in the shared audit log, including the output description, decision, justification, reviewer initials, and a link to the service desk ticket. This log supports consistency across reviewers and serves as an accessible precedent base for future cases.

Decisions are recorded as Yes, Yes but..., or No.

A “Yes, but...” outcome indicates that additional disclosure management is required before approval. This always involves an iterative exchange between the primary reviewer and the researcher to agree and apply measures such as rounding, suppression, masking or other safe-release techniques. Once these mitigations are complete, the decision is finalised as Yes or No.

A “No” outcome is accompanied by guidance on how the output could be revised to move towards approval. Researchers may request escalation via the standard process. Borderline or novel cases are referred to the Data Management Team. Where the matter is still unresolved or outside existing precedent, then to the DAC Chair for a final governance determination.

After the decisions and evidence are recorded in the audit log the approved outputs can be made available for the researcher to download.

4.3. Researcher training

Researcher training¹¹ combines foundational SDC principles with practical guidance on using ACRO and SACRO within analytical workflows. The aim is to help research teams recognise disclosure risks early, apply standard mitigations during analysis, and submit outputs with sufficient context to support efficient review through the airlock process.

Training is integrated into the broader EE-SDE onboarding process and is delivered when researchers are beginning to design analytical workflows and produce draft outputs. An initial onboarding introduction familiarises research teams with the EE-SDE environment, outlines expectations for output checking, and introduces the concept of disclosure-aware analysis. At this stage, researchers are also informed that a

synthetic dataset is available within the research environment, allowing them to safely experiment with analytical workflows and understand disclosure risks before working with project data.

A dedicated SDC session is also delivered as a follow up to the onboarding. This session introduces the principles of SDC and demonstrates how ACRO can be incorporated into common analytical workflows in Python or R. Researchers are guided through typical disclosure risks such as small cell counts, excessive stratification, dominance and secondary disclosure and the practical mitigations used to reduce risk, including aggregation, suppression, rounding and binning. The session also introduces the role of SACRO within the output-review process and explains how structured outputs produced by ACRO support more consistent disclosure assessment.

Training includes demonstrations using a synthetic OMOP-style dataset available within the Research Environment. Example Python notebooks and R scripts show how ACRO can be used alongside familiar analytical tools to generate tables, plots and model outputs while automatically applying disclosure checks. Researchers also learn how to manage outputs prior to submission, including the preparation of appropriate contextual notes, removing unnecessary outputs and finalising sessions to produce standardised artefacts for egress.

All training materials are hosted in the EE-SDE knowledge base so researchers can revisit guidance during analysis. Additional support is available through the EE-SDE service desk via a ticketing system, enabling researchers to request clarification and allowing the EE-SDE team to maintain a documented support trail.

4.4. Researcher documentation

The EE-SDE provides a self-serve, action-oriented knowledge base¹² that supports researchers in understanding how to egress research outputs from the platform and apply SDC within their analytical work (Figure 2). These materials sit within the platform's knowledge base and build on the onboarding training that researchers receive when joining the EE-SDE, as well as any other safe-outputs training that forms part of their professional background. The intention is that the documentation becomes a practical companion during day-to-day analysis, rather than an isolated reference that is only consulted at the point of egress.

The guidance complements the formal, community-maintained resources that underpin safe-outputs practice. Where appropriate, the documentation directs researchers to the SACRO guide, the SDC Handbook, and the wider ecosystem of authoritative materials that describe core SDC principles and explain the underlying behaviour of ACRO. As these foundational resources evolve, the EE-SDE documentation will be reviewed and updated so that it remains aligned with current standards and incorporates the latest explanations, examples and best-practice recommendations.

At its core, the researcher documentation explains why SDC is required and how to apply it effectively before submitting an egress request. It sets out the key risks that need to be avoided, including direct identification, attribute disclosure involving small groups and secondary disclosure when new outputs can be combined with earlier releases. The guidance highlights common patterns that give rise to these issues and presents straightforward mitigations. These include reducing unnecessary stratification, checking for small or sparse cells, considering potential reconstruction routes when using suppression and reviewing figures or narrative sections to ensure that rare individuals are not inadvertently identifiable. Where helpful, researchers are encouraged to use tools such as Statbarn to anticipate disclosive patterns and select appropriate mitigations early in the analysis.

Figure 2: Overview of researcher output preparation pathways within the EE-SDE, comparing standard manual disclosure control with SACRO-assisted workflows prior to airlock review and release.

Where analyses can be wrapped with ACRO in Python, R or Stata, the documentation encourages researchers to adopt these workflows because they incorporate standardised disclosure safeguards. However, the materials emphasise that ACRO does not absolve the researcher of responsibility for contextual judgement. The outputs of automated tools must still be assessed carefully, particularly where the population being analysed is small or where multiple outputs could be drawn together in ways that introduce new risks.

As the airlock submission form offers limited space for describing analytical intent, the documentation highlights the importance of including a well-constructed README with each request. This short file is used by airlock managers to understand both the purpose of the output and the SDC steps that have already been applied. Researchers are asked to describe the output type, how the work aligns with the approved project scope, the SDC techniques used, any secondary-risk considerations and whether ACRO was used to generate the files. Requests lacking this information are returned for clarification, so the guidance provides examples that can be adapted to different analytical contexts.

The practical egress instructions are designed to help researchers prepare their files correctly on the first attempt. Users who do not yet have airlock permissions are guided to request access in advance. The documentation then explains how to stage files in the designated read and write egress area, noting that files cannot be renamed or replaced once copied. Researchers are shown how to create a transfer in the egress system of the platform, how to specify paths relative to the egress folder and how to attach their README.

After submission, the file list must be reviewed during the source-review stage. If corrections are required, the request should be denied and resubmitted rather than amended piecemeal.

By combining clear explanations, practical examples, references to authoritative SDC resources and stepwise platform guidance, the documentation supports researchers in making SDC part of routine analytical practice. This self-serve model ensures that users can independently prepare safe, well-described outputs that progress smoothly through airlock review and align with both EE-SDE procedures and broader community standards.

5. Feedback and process improvement

The introduction of SACRO within the EE-SDE has generated demonstrable benefits for both researchers and airlock managers, especially in relation to descriptive statistical outputs. It has shifted disclosure control from a largely manual practice to a more standardised and auditable process. ACRO produces many commonly used outputs with automated checks already applied, and these are packaged with helpful metadata and logs. When these structured artefacts reach the airlock, reviewers receive a consistent evidence bundle that makes their work more efficient and straightforward. This has been especially useful for routine tables and standard regression results, where SACRO presents the underlying risk profile in a format that is easy to interpret.

Reviewers noted that SACRO is particularly helpful during triage. It immediately highlights whether an output requires closer scrutiny, and its flags and contextual notes help reviewers focus their attention effectively. The tool enhances reviewer judgement by removing much of the detective work involved in understanding large and complex outputs. What SACRO provides is not automation of decisions, but a more intelligible starting point.

While these benefits are substantial, testing and real-world use have also highlighted areas where SACRO does not yet align with the full range of analytical practices in the EE-SDE. These limitations affect both user groups and influence the overall efficiency of the egress pipeline.

5.1. Airlock manager feedback

Airlock managers reported that SACRO makes reviewing supported outputs more efficient. They observed that the combination of structured workflows, automated checks, and clear exception reporting allows many low-risk outputs to be approved within one to two working days, compared with the typical three to five days required for fully manual review. However, they also highlighted challenges when dealing with mixed submissions. Many egress requests contain a blend of ACRO checked artefacts and manually generated outputs. This requires reviewers to switch between SACRO Viewer and the file system with manual inspection. Although the SOP distinguishes between the two routes, reviewers must frequently move between them within a single submission, which increases workload and slows decisions.

Another concern was that SACRO artefacts do not yet cover all the risks airlock managers must consider. Even when an ACRO output receives a positive assessment, reviewers must still check for contextual or secondary disclosure risks that SACRO cannot assess. In practice, this involves reviewing outputs in relation to other tables, previous releases, and the broader analytical context to identify risks such as differencing or

residual disclosure. Enhancing guidance and reviewer prompts for assessing secondary disclosure risk represents a valuable opportunity to further strengthen the EE-SDE review process. While the current documentation outlines these principles, reviewers noted that the SACRO Viewer interface could incorporate structured review prompts to guide airlock managers through both automated checks and required manual assessment, clearly indicating what has been assessed and what requires further judgement, particularly for secondary disclosure risks.

As SACRO continues to be used across a growing number of projects, further insights are expected to emerge. This will support ongoing refinement of reviewer guidance, SOPs, and tooling, ensuring that the output-checking process continues to evolve in line with the complexity and scale of research conducted within the EE-SDE.

5.2. Researcher feedback

Researchers found ACRO straightforward to integrate into their existing R workflows. Functions such as `acro_table()` and `acro_glm()` closely resemble the commands analysts already use, so adopting SACRO required very little alteration to established scripts. This ease of integration encouraged researchers to incorporate disclosure control thinking throughout their work rather than treating it as something that only needs attention at the point of egress. Automated checks on common outputs, including frequency tables, standard regression results and some survival analyses, worked reliably and removed a considerable amount of manual checking that would otherwise have been required.

The logging functionality built into ACRO was another feature researchers valued. By recording every output created during an analytical session, it provided a transparent history of what had been generated and reduced the risk of version mismatches between what a researcher intended to submit for egress and what was actually created. Researchers also appreciated that ACRO actively supported their understanding of disclosure control principles by flagging small groups or sparse categories as they appeared. This immediate, in context feedback helped reinforce good practice in a way that written guidance alone cannot achieve.

Alongside these strengths, researchers also highlighted important limitations in how far SACRO currently supports the full range of analytical work carried out in the EE-SDE. Many commonly used outputs fall outside SACRO's automated assessment, particularly visualisations. Bar charts, scatter plots, box plots and forest plots must all undergo manual review, and even histograms, which SACRO does assess, return only a generic review warning, making it difficult for researchers to understand the specific disclosure risk. For projects that rely heavily on visual exploration or need publication ready graphics, this makes it difficult to stay fully within the SACRO workflow.

Researchers also pointed to gaps in method coverage. While ACRO supports logistic and probit regression, it does not extend to often used methods such as Poisson regression, spline-based approaches, nonlinear terms or multiple imputation. When an analysis requires these techniques, researchers must step out of the ACRO environment, fragmenting the workflow and potentially introducing inconsistencies in the way disclosure control is applied. Although a custom output route exists, it does not apply automated checks, so it offers little benefit in terms of SDC assurance.

A related point concerns documentation for visual outputs. The [sacrotools](#) documentation provides a strong conceptual foundation, but it does not yet offer clear, tasks specific guidance on how to tailor plots for publication, for example adjusting labels, axes or layout. Without this practical detail, researchers often choose to create visualisations outside ACRO, which means they lose access to SACRO's automated checks and risk drifting away from the structured workflows that SACRO aims to support. Similarly, analysts noted that creating baseline descriptive tables is more cumbersome in ACRO than in other established R packages, increasing the chance of manual errors.

Taken together, these findings show that SACRO delivers meaningful value for a subset of routine statistical outputs, particularly well-defined descriptive and regression results. However, it is not yet equipped to provide comprehensive disclosure control across the full analytical lifecycle. More complex, bespoke or publication focused outputs still require manual review, and researchers must frequently combine SACRO supported and unsupported methods within the same project. For these reasons, SACRO currently complements rather than replaces human judgement and manual disclosure control expertise within the EE-SDE.

5.3.EE-SDE Process improvements

The combined experience of users points to several improvements that could strengthen the egress pathway.

A priority is to integrate SACRO outputs into a single, broader egress and audit tool rather than relying on a standalone viewer. This would allow all outputs, whether produced through ACRO or not, to be viewed and assessed in one place. SACRO artefacts would still contribute the structured assessment they are designed to provide, but reviewers would not need to switch between tools. This would make the workflow more coherent, improve oversight and increase transparency for all output types.

There is also an opportunity to strengthen the way researchers provide the contextual information required during egress. The current airlock interface is limited and relies heavily on free text READMEs, which vary in quality and frequently require follow-up. The EE-SDE intends to improve this interface so that essential information is captured in a structured, consistent format. This will reduce the likelihood of missing information and shorten the review process.

Together, these developments point toward an egress system that is more integrated and more intuitive. Reducing the visible divide between ACRO and non-ACRO outputs will help create a unified review flow. Strengthening researcher interfaces will improve submission quality and help reduce delays. These steps, taken together, will help ensure that SACRO continues to bring value while the wider egress process becomes more efficient, consistent and transparent.

6. Scaling disclosure control within and between TREs

6.1. Scaling within the EE-SDE

As research activity within the EE-SDE continues to grow, the volume and variety of outputs requiring disclosure review will increase. To meet this demand, the EE-SDE will require approaches that maintain

consistent and auditable SDC without adding disproportionate workload for reviewers. SACRO contributes to this by offering structured, semi-automated checks for suitable statistical outputs, while operational processes and governance frameworks ensure that results remain reliable and defensible as the service scales.

One-way SACRO supports scalability is through its structured risk indicators. Outputs generated through ACRO include clear summaries showing whether any disclosure thresholds have been triggered. These flags help airlock managers prioritise their efforts, allowing low risk outputs to be reviewed quickly while directing more time toward those that warrant deeper scrutiny. This triage model supports a proportional workload as submissions increase.

The EE-SDE is also strengthening scalability through the development of a shared audit log. By assigning unique identifiers to common output types and linking them to past disclosure decisions, the system will gradually build a useful library of precedents. Airlock managers will be able to draw on this history when reviewing similar outputs, reducing duplication of effort and providing new reviewers with a structured way to build confidence and consistency. This approach sits alongside ongoing work to expand shared training and shared policies across teams, ensuring that reviewers follow consistent principles regardless of experience level. To reinforce this consistency, the EE-SDE will also introduce six-monthly disclosure-control consistency checks, reviewing a sample of past decisions to ensure quality is maintained and that assessments remain aligned across all airlock managers.

Researchers also play a critical role in scaling the process. SACRO Viewer gives researchers a structured way to explore potential risks during analysis, which helps resolve common issues before submission and reduces the need for revisions once an egress request is raised. Moving forward, the EE-SDE will support researchers to complete early disclosure risk assessments using tools such as Statbarn. This will help teams understand likely risks at the start of their analysis, anticipate where small groups or sparse categories may appear, and adjust methods or presentation choices early, rather than late in the workflow. Together with shared training resources that provide a common grounding in SDC principles, it is anticipated that this early, tool-assisted approach will improve the quality of outputs entering review and shorten turnaround times through the airlock.

6.2. Scaling across TREs

Although TREs differ in their governance models, risk appetites and disclosure thresholds, most already work in line with the recognised principles of SDC. In many cases, however, this is applied through locally developed, ad hoc practices that vary between teams and can be difficult to scale or explain transparently. As TRE activity grows, these informal approaches can place pressure on reviewers, increase variability in decision making and make it harder for researchers to understand expectations when moving between environments.

The EE-SDE's approach, which combines clearly written SOPs, structured documentation and the use of SACRO where appropriate, offers a way to move from these disparate practices toward a more consistent and sustainable framework. By grounding operational processes in shared principles such as primary disclosure, attribute disclosure and secondary disclosure, TREs can work from a common conceptual

foundation while still accommodating local governance requirements. This shared language improves the clarity of discussions about risk and supports more consistent interpretation of outputs, even when TREs differ in appetite or policy.

For researchers, the priority is to support consistent application of core SDC principles across TREs, reducing the need for repeated retraining. By recognising shared training, such as the ONS Safe Researcher training¹³ or equivalent accredited modules, TREs can accept a common baseline of knowledge and focus local onboarding on how those principles are applied within each environment. This reduces duplication, shortens time to productivity and helps researchers move between TREs with a consistent understanding of disclosure risk, while site specific guidance covers local thresholds, policies and submission steps.

For reviewers, shared policies and coherent training materials help ensure that outputs are assessed in comparable ways across TREs, which is increasingly important as cross site and collaborative research becomes more common.

Shared training and guidance also provide an opportunity to reduce duplicated effort across the TRE community. Resources such as the SDC Handbook, Statbarn and the SACRO documentation already offer high-quality explanations of disclosure risks and mitigation strategies. Using these widely recognised materials as the basis for both researcher and reviewer training allows TREs to build consistent capability across their teams while avoiding the need to develop bespoke training for each environment. A shared, unified resource base helps ensure that staff bring a consistent understanding of safe outputs practice wherever they work, while frameworks such as the EE-SDE's SOPs and SACRO provide a scalable and transparent operational model that can be adopted or adapted by other TREs.

7. Impact

The use of SACRO has transitioned the EE-SDE's safe outputs process for descriptive statistics from predominantly manual checks to a more structured and auditable service. Researchers can generate routine outputs in ACRO that arrive at the airlock with metadata, logs and clear risk summaries, giving reviewers a consistent evidence bundle at the point of egress. This has improved clarity, reduced rework and enabled faster triage for straightforward tables and standard models, with risk information presented in a predictable format that supports human judgement rather than replacing it.

For researchers, ACRO's wrappers mirror familiar R and Python workflows, lowering the barrier to adoption and encouraging disclosure aware practice during analysis, not only at submission. Built-in logging provides a traceable record of what was produced, improving reproducibility and alignment between generated outputs and what is submitted for review.

For airlock managers, SACRO has strengthened triage and brought greater consistency to decisions on supported output types. Risk indicators and structured artefacts help reviewers focus attention where it is most needed, reducing routine manual inspection and shortening turnaround times for clearly safe outputs. Decisions remain human and are backed by clearer evidence, which strengthens assurance and defensibility.

Governance has been strengthened by making the basis for decisions more explicit. ACRO artefacts show the risk settings applied, and reviewer rationales are recorded in a shared audit log, creating a repeatable pathway from submission to sign-off that is easier to explain to researchers, auditors and public contributors.

The approach also lays foundations for scale. As volumes increase, structured risk summaries support proportional triage and reduce unnecessary effort. The audit log is evolving into a precedent library that promotes consistent outcomes and helps onboard new reviewers more quickly. Researchers are encouraged to assess risk earlier in their work using SACRO Viewer and tools such as Statbarn⁴ so that likely issues are addressed before egress requests are raised. Together these steps increase throughput without diluting oversight.

Experience from live use points to pragmatic next steps that will amplify impact. Integrating SACRO outputs into a broader egress and audit tool will allow all output types to be reviewed in one place, improving transparency and reducing tool switching. Enhancing the researcher interface to capture structured context at submission will reduce reliance on free text READMEs and shorten review cycles.

Taken together, the workstream shows how semi-automated disclosure checking can operate in production while keeping human oversight at the centre. The combination of shared SDC principles, clear SOPs, task-based platform guidance and SACRO artefacts provides a transferable blueprint that other TREs can adopt or adapt to move from ad hoc practice toward a sustainable, transparent framework for safe outputs.

8. Audience and contributions

This workstream was delivered by airlock managers from the EE-SDE team, supported by contributions from the research governance team and the SACRO developers. It was informed by feedback from external researchers. The primary audience for these outputs is TRE operational teams, particularly airlock managers responsible for overseeing the safe egress of data. The materials may also be valuable to other members of the TRE community, including data controllers and researchers, by helping them understand the key considerations involved in managing disclosure risks when egressing research outputs from a TRE.

9. Conclusions and future direction

The SACRO workstream has strengthened safe outputs practice within the EE-SDE by turning what was largely a manual, interpretive activity into a more structured, transparent and auditable process. Researchers can generate many descriptive statistical outputs using ACRO and submit them with clear risk summaries, metadata and logs, which in turn enables airlock managers to triage efficiently and base decisions on consistent evidence. The combination of task-based platform guidance, shared SDC principles and role specific training has embedded disclosure awareness earlier in analysis and made decisions easier to explain to researchers, auditors and public contributors. Together these processes provide a solid foundation for scaling safe, efficient output review as activity grows.

Equally important, the workstream has clarified where automation is not yet appropriate or implemented for all analytical outputs. Rather than viewing these as shortcomings, we see them as a roadmap for targeted

improvement. As our service scales and our understanding of the statistical methods used by research teams deepens, we will iteratively extend wrapper coverage where proportionate, enhance task level documentation for activities that remain outside automation, and integrate SACRO artefacts into a single egress and audit experience so all outputs are reviewed in one place. This will reduce tool switching, improve transparency and support consistent recording of reviewer rationales. We will also enhance the researcher interface to capture essential context in a structured way, reducing reliance on free text READMEs and lowering the risk of avoidable rework. In parallel, we will continue to promote early risk assessment during analysis, encouraging teams to use SACRO Viewer and community tools such as Statbarn to anticipate issues and adjust methods or presentation choices before raising an egress request. These actions will be guided by routine measurement of cycle times, rework rates and decision consistency, and by structured user feedback.

Looking beyond the EE-SDE, the workstream offers a practical path that other TREs can adopt or adapt to move from ad hoc practice toward a sustainable and transparent framework grounded in shared SDC principles. We will work with partners across the TRE community to align on a common language for disclosure risk while respecting local governance, thresholds and risk appetites. By sharing our SOPs, decision frameworks and audit log patterns, and by contributing to a shared precedent library, we aim to improve comparability of decisions and support cross-site research. We will also advocate for a single point of lookup that brings together disclosure risk concepts, SACRO materials and exemplar workflows, so TREs can reference a uniform resource rather than multiple locations.

A further priority is strengthening researcher capability. To reduce repetition during onboarding, we will work with the network to recognise shared training such as the ONS Safe Researcher course and equivalent accredited modules, as a common baseline. Local onboarding can then focus on how widely accepted SDC principles apply within each environment, improving time to productivity and reducing duplication. We will couple this with short, role specific refreshers for researchers and airlock managers on topics such as secondary disclosure and preparing publication ready outputs without stepping outside safe outputs workflows.

In summary, SACRO has advanced the speed, consistency and auditability of supported outputs in the EE-SDE while also clarifying roles and strengthening public facing assurance. Our future focus is on continuous improvement as the service scales, deeper integration of SACRO within egress, clearer guidance for complex analyses and sustained collaboration with other TREs to raise transparency and structure across the wider community.

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11. Glossary

Airlock manager - A data security role in Trusted Research Environments, responsible for reviewing and approving data transfers in and out of the TRE.

CPAG - Core Public Advisory Group, the patient and public advisory group established for the Eastern England Secure Data Environment.

CUH - Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust

CUHP - Cambridge University Health Partners, academic health science centre with a mission to improve patient care by uniting the NHS, Industry and Academia

DAC - Data Access Committee, the group of governance, subject matter experts and members of the public who review and make access decisions for a given TRE.

DAR - Data Access Request, the form or document completed by a researcher to describe their research question and data needs so an access decision can be made for a given TRE.

DARE UK - Data and Analytics Research Environments UK, is a programme aimed towards establishing a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments.

EE-SDE - Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

Egress - The controlled process of releasing data or analytical outputs from a secure environment (such as an SDE or TRE) following review and approval to ensure that no disclosure risks are present.

Five Safes - A widely used framework for designing and assessing safe access to sensitive data across five dimensions: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data and Safe Outputs (considered together to achieve "safe use")

Four-Eyes Principle - A governance control requiring independent review by a second reviewer to ensure consistency and reduce the risk of error in decision-making.

HIE - Health Innovation East, the innovation arm of the NHS in the East of England.

ML (Machine Learning) – A set of computational methods that enable systems to learn patterns from data and make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed.

OMOP – Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model, is a standardised data model used to structure healthcare data in a consistent format across different organisations. It enables researchers to perform analyses using the same definitions, tables, and coding systems (e.g. SNOMED, LOINC), improving reproducibility and comparability of results within secure environments such as the EE-SDE.

PPIE – Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement is the active partnership between researchers and the public to shape health research.

SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and ML, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained ML models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SafeModel – A wrapper around a machine learning model in SACRO-ML that enforces disclosure risk checks and records information needed to assess whether the model is safe to release.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

SDC handbook – A guidance resource that outlines principles and methods for Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC), providing practical approaches to identifying and mitigating disclosure risks in statistical outputs before release.

Thresholds – Predefined minimum values or limits used in Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) to determine whether an output can be safely released. Commonly applied to counts (e.g. minimum cell size such as ≥ 10), thresholds help prevent identification of individuals by ensuring that groups are sufficiently large and not disclosive.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

UKRI - UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT).

VISTA – Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI, is the project package aimed towards delivering tools to enhance Statistical Disclosure Checking, support in TREs for ML, and also for establishing a benchmarking standard for Trusted Research Environments.

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Appendix 1 - SACRO usability review

Overview

Research Focus: Anaemia Risk Factors & Healthcare Utilisation

Research Data: OMOP 50K from <https://registry.opendata.aws/synthea-omop>

Research Question:

Which demographic and clinical factors are associated with anaemia, and do Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), hypertension, and heart failure independently or jointly modify that risk? How well can machine learning (Random Forest) predict anaemia status using these factors?

Rationale

Anaemia is a common condition with significant morbidity. Understanding its risk factors helps guide screening, management, and healthcare planning.

The OMOP CDM provides structured, multi-domain data: condition_occurrence, measurement (haemoglobin), drug_exposure, visit_occurrence which enables in multi-level analyses (prevalence, regression, survival, count outcomes) without extensive data wrangling.

Supports both binary outcome (anaemia yes/no) and time-to-event analysis (time to anaemia).

Interaction terms (T2DM × HF) test effect modification and ACRO/SACRO suppression thresholds.

Random Forest models allow evaluation of predictive performance

Generates outputs of varying complexity, ideal for testing ACRO usability and SDC safeguards.

Analysis Planning

Statistical hypothesis tests such as t-tests, ANOVA, and correlation tests generally present low disclosure risk, as they report aggregated test statistics rather than individual-level data hence I've not tested them.

Method	Purpose	ACRO / R function
Descriptive frequency tables	Prevalence of anaemia by age, gender, comorbidity	acro_table()
Logistic regression (GLM)	Identify independent predictors of anaemia (ORs + CIs)	acro_glm()
Interaction model	Test T2DM × HF interaction on anaemia risk	acro_glm()

Kaplan-Meier survival analysis	Time-to-anaemia diagnosis stratified by comorbidities	acro_surv_func()
Poisson regression	Count outcome: comorbidity burden	R (glm)
Random Forest	Predict Anemia Status	randomForest(manual plotting of feature importance, ROC, confusion matrix)

Table 1: Statistical methods

Plot Type	Purpose / Insights	Method / Function
Age Histogram	Visualize distribution of cohort age	acro_hist()
Anaemia Prevalence by Comorbidity Count	Show proportion of anaemia across number of comorbidities	ggplot2::geom_bar
Anaemia Prevalence by Gender	Compare anaemia rates between males and females	acro_table() + bar chart via ggplot2
Anaemia Prevalence by T2DM, HTN, HF	Explore prevalence across individual comorbidities	acro_table() + bar charts via ggplot2
Box Plot: Follow-up Days	To assess whether patients with multiple conditions have longer or shorter follow-up periods	ggplot2
Logistic Regression Forest Plot (ORs + CIs)	Visualize odds ratios from logistic regression	glm()+ggplot2
Poisson Regression Forest Plot	Show incidence rate ratios (IRR) for comorbidity count	glm()+ggplot2
Random Forest Feature Importance	Identify most predictive features for anaemia	randomForest::varImpPlot() + ggplot2
ROC Curve (Random Forest)	Evaluate predictive performance of model	pROC::roc() + ggplot2

Table 2: plots and charts created

Output Generation & Egress Consideration

Output type	SACRO	StatBarn Category	Risks and SDC considerations
Frequency table (anaemia x clinical and demographic variables)	Yes	Frequencies	High, Unsafe, needs suppression if counts are low (e.g., <10) and manual review of marginal totals. ACRO suppresses it automatically
Histograms (age, haemoglobin, followup)	Yes	Frequencies/Shape	Low, Unsafe, each bin is a frequency; bins with small counts risk disclosure.
Box plots (follow-up/age vs comorbidity × anaemia)	No	Position (median/IQR)	Medium, Unsafe, Small subgroup sizes may reveal rare combinations; annotate or suppress boxes if n<10.
Bar charts (anaemia prevalence by comorbidity / age / gender)	No	Frequencies	Low, unsafe, ensure no bar segment represents <10 individuals; ACRO cannot automatically check ggplot2 plots.
Logistic regression coefficients (ORs + CIs)	Yes	Odds and risk ratios	Low, Safe, if underlying n sufficient; check for very small strata.
Interaction model (T2DM × HF)	Yes	Odds and risk ratios	Medium, Unsafe, Interaction subgroups may be very small; manual review recommended.
Poisson regression (IRR)	No	Odds and risk ratios	Safe if underlying counts are adequate.
Forest plot (Logistic regression Ors, poisson)	No	Odds and risk ratios	Low, Safe, Displays Ors, IIRs, and CIs from regression models. Safe provided model estimates are not derived from very small strata, manual check needed before egress.
Kaplan-Meier survival curve and table	Yes	Survival tables	Medium, unsafe, Tail of curve with <10 at risk must be

			censored; manual plot review required.
Random Forest feature importance	No	Not defined statbarn	Medium, unsafe, SACRO-ML supports model type, but feature importance may reveal small subgroups; top-N features recommended.
ROC curves	No	Frequencies / Shape	Medium, Unsafe, Extreme thresholds can correspond to very small groups; manual review needed.

Feedback

What went well

1. Implementing standard statistical analyses such as descriptive tables and regression models was straightforward using functions like `acro_table()` or `acro_pivot_table()` and `acro_glm()`. These functions closely mirror base R workflows, so minimal changes to the analysis script were required
2. Frequency tables and summary statistics were automatically checked for disclosure risk, which simplified compliance with statistical disclosure control requirements
3. The ACRO logging system allowed outputs generated during the session to be tracked, which helps maintain transparency and supports the review process before egress

Challenges

1. Graphical outputs required manual disclosure checking because SACRO does not currently provide automated checking for plots created with `ggplot2`. Apart from Histograms ACRO doesn't support any SDC for plots (e.g., box plots, scatter plots, and forest plots) therefore needed careful manual review
2. Extracting regression results for visualization (e.g., forest plots) is not supported when models were generated through ACRO
3. `acro_glm()` currently supports only logit and probit models, which limits its use for other generalized linear models such as Poisson regression and additional model families
4. Commonly used additional modelling approaches such as non-linear modelling, spline terms, or multiple imputation to handle missing data. These approaches are not directly supported by SACRO wrappers
5. One practical note for troubleshooting: when using ACRO in R, the **reticulate** library is required. Without it, the session cannot be initialized, which can prevent the package from running properly. Mentioning this in the documentation or setup instructions would help users avoid this common setup issue

Summary

Testing ACRO within an R-based analytical workflow provided additional insight into how semi-automated disclosure checking performs across a range of commonly used analytical outputs. The testing included descriptive frequency tables, logistic regression models, interaction models, survival analysis, Poisson regression, and machine learning outputs, allowing the workflow to be evaluated across both standard statistical outputs and more complex analytical results.

ACRO functions such as `acro_table()` and `acro_glm()` closely mirror standard R analysis functions, enabling disclosure-checked outputs to be generated with minimal modification to existing analysis scripts. Structured outputs such as frequency tables and regression summaries were automatically evaluated against disclosure thresholds, reducing the need for manual inspection during the output review process. ACRO's logging functionality also recorded outputs generated during the session, providing traceability that can support the Airlock review process prior to egress.

The testing also identified outputs that remain outside the scope of automated disclosure checks. Graphical outputs produced using `ggplot2`, including box plots, scatter plots, bar charts, and forest plots, are not currently subject to automated disclosure checking. While ACRO can assess tabular outputs underlying certain plots such as histograms, most visualisations require manual review to ensure that small subgroup sizes or rare combinations are not inadvertently disclosed.

Additional limitations were observed in the scope of modelling approaches supported by ACRO wrapper functions. While `acro_glm()` supports logit and probit models, other commonly used analytical methods, such as Poisson regression, spline-based models, and techniques used to address missing data may require analysts to generate outputs outside the ACRO wrapper framework. In these cases, disclosure control assessment relies on manual review of the resulting outputs before egress. The testing demonstrated that ACRO can substantially streamline disclosure checking for structured statistical outputs while remaining compatible with existing analytical workflows. At the same time, the results confirm that automated checks complement rather than replace manual Statistical Disclosure Control review, particularly for complex visualisations and analytical outputs that fall outside the current scope of automated checks.